

O'smirlarda destruktiv xulq ko'rishlari shakllanishining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada voyaga yetmagan o'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarda dunyo bo'ylab tarqalgan destruktiv xulq-atvor ko'rinishlarini shakllanishi hamda ularga to'g'ri diagnoz qo'yish, ular korreksiya ishlarini olib boorish bo'yicha ma'lumotlar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: destruktiv xulq, buzg'unchi faoliyat, disfunktsional oila, ijtimoiy ta'sir, shaxs, ong va ongsizlik

Introduction By the middle of the 20th century, the problem of destructive behavior began to take shape. The psychological approach was focused on the separation of socio-psychological disparity of individual manifestations in the destructive behavior of adolescent students. Destructive behavior is a behavior pattern directed towards negating any alternative thoughts that contradict the social behavior patterns perceived in society. Destructive behavior, on the other hand, is verbal or other manifestations of internal activity aimed at destroying something. Elimination covers all areas of personality: socialization, health, relationships are important people. Such behavior leads to a deterioration in the quality of the presence of an individual, a decrease in2023232critical attitude to one's own actions, cognitive disturbances in the perception and interpretation of what is happening, a decrease in self-esteem and emotional disorders.This often leads to social adaptation, up to the absolute isolation of the individual. Such behavior is sometimes the result of a defense mechanism that consists of detecting an aggressor. The considered change in behavior is characterized by a deviation from the norms of behavior and morality adopted by society.It is common to divide behavioral patterns into disruptive or abnormal behaviors and constructive (normal), generally accepted behaviors. Abnormal behavior that forms destructively is characterized by non-standard, Pathology-Limited, dissatisfaction with society. This is often a deviation from the point of view of social guidelines, medical norms, psychological attitudes.Literature analysisEach model of behavior is formed in childhood. A four-to five-year-old baby studies the information that determines his further relationship with the social environment. A full-fledged family,

dominated by mutual understanding, care, attention, love has a beneficial effect on the maturation of the psyche of babies, laying the foundation for patterns of behavior. Therefore, individuals who do not receive adequate education, warmth, attention, love fall into the category of danger. You should also know that children often take a pattern of destructive behavior from their parents. Scientists have found that the destructive behavior of an individual is successfully formed against the background of the presence of the following factors:-the presence of many social deviations (bureaucracy, corruption, drunkenness, crime);-liberalization of measures of social influence (body, lowering the level of criticism);-situation anomalies(speculation, fictitious marriages;-weakening measures to combat abnormal behavior (lack of fines, punishment systems).

Freud was convinced that destructive behavior was the result of a person's negative attitude towards their own person. He also noted that the crash was one of the main drivers. Proponents of psychoanalytic theory have argued that supernatural actions are inherent to all subjects of a person to varying degrees, except that the objects of such actions (other personified or inanimate objects or his own) differ. Adler has a similar view, which he believes is the primary reason for disruptive behavior being a sense of alienation and non-existence. Fromm argues that deviant behavior triggers an unrealized human potential, as well as failing to use effective energy for its own purpose. Durkheim made a social analysis of the variability of the behavioral response under consideration. While Merton wrote that the disruptive behavior anomie was related to a special moral and psychological state characterized by the collapse of a system of moral values and spiritual guidance, Worsley, in turn, explored the relativism of the relationship between sociocultural norms and "absolute" standards. Research methodology The problem of self-destruction of adolescents is very relevant, since it leads to addiction, suicide attempts by adolescents, alcoholism. Over the years, the number of children has been increasing. Cases of drug addiction, alcoholism of minors have long been not surprising to anyone. In addition, the described problems are observed not only in families in difficult situations. Statistical observations say that about 37% of children are treated for drug addiction medical institution registered, coming from much more prosperous families.

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